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The role of digital twin technology in transforming and managing industrial supply chain risks

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Investigating the impact of digital twins (DT) on supply chain resilience in economic crises or unexpected changes such as a pandemic is a current research challenge.

The paper aims to analyze the potential applications of DT in supply chain formation.

Materials and Methods. The study materials were research articles from peer-reviewed journals covering the latest developments in digital twins. The article uses a case method (the example of the Siemens Company).

Research Findings. With the help of DT technologies, today's industry is empowered to solve a wide range of online problems covering all interrelated aspects of the enterprise: research and development, manufacturing and assembly, marketing and sales. As awareness of the economic benefits of DT technology grows, its application will increase in various fields to drive industrial restructuring and modernization.

Conclusion. Using DT in supply chain optimization has several advantages. In particular, manufacturing companies can use DT to optimize processes, reduce costs, and improve efficiency. Real-time route optimization and inventory management can minimize delays and congestion.

The role of DT in supply chain optimization is becoming increasingly important. They can significantly reduce risk, improve efficiency, and promote flexibility. Implementing such technologies will undoubtedly be a hot topic for research and practical initiatives in the coming years.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the research topic is due to the rapid development of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, and artificial intelligence. Digital twins (DT), virtual replicas of physical objects or processes, allow these technologies to be integrated into supply chains to increase efficiency.

DT can analyze current data and simulate different scenarios, allowing companies to predict demand better, minimize inventory and avoid product shortages. This is especially relevant in volatile markets.

Thanks to the high granularity of DT, companies can identify bottlenecks in their processes by analyzing time and resources. This reduces costs and increases productivity.

DT can help identify potential risks and supply chain issues before they occur, which allows preparing for possible disruptions in advance.

Companies that successfully implement DT have an advantage over their competitors due to increased responsiveness to market changes and reduced operational costs.

Thus, research into the role of DT in supply chains is relevant and critical to improving the efficiency and sustainability of modern business models.

Literature review

Digital twins are virtual models of physical objects or systems. This literature review will help further understand how they function and the technologies used to create them.

J. E. Aguilar-Ramirez et al. identify the main characteristics of DT and Blockchain technologies and how they can meet supply chain needs. The authors point out the advantages and disadvantages that are to be appropriately analyzed before implementing this approach in any business [1].

A. Pennisi di Floristella & X. Chen write that the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and the European Union view sustainability as a departure from past doctrines of pure economic efficiency. Still, each has a different understanding and approach to supply chain sustainability. Despite some differences, both coalitions view sustainability and digital transformation as critical components of supply chain sustainability to improve economic cooperation and strategic partnerships [2].

As reflected in academic periodicals, let us look at specific examples of DT applications in different industries.

L. Wang et al. discuss the possibilities of supply chain modeling, real-time supply chain optimization, and use of data in supply chain collaboration. The authors provide an example this model being successfully implemented in China's largest retailer JD.com [3].

J. A. Marmolejo-Saucedo proposes integration of large-scale optimization tasks into a digital platform that solves these tasks for real-time decision making. Container packing and vehicle routing tasks are solved using a commercial supply chain management platform interface and heuristic optimization algorithms [4].

L. Tebaldi et al. give a literature review on sources regarding DT models in the context of agri-food supply chain [5].

D. A. Howard et al. created the Greenhouse Industry 4.0 Digital Twin software platform to combine Industry 4.0 technologies (IoT, AI, Big Data, cloud computing and DT) as integrated parts of greenhouse production systems. Applying this model to the Danish horticultural greenhouse industry provides digital models to simulate and evaluate the performance of a physical greenhouse facility. The DT ecosystem extends current technology by adopting a scalable distributed 'system of systems' approach that links DT in a production facility. A set of specialized DT is linked to describe and model all aspects of the production chain, such as total production capacity, energy consumption, delivery dates, and delivery [6].

C. Shrivastava et al. developed a DT for citrus to determine precisely when, why and to what extent the quality and marketability of these fruits decline. According to the authors, half of the supply is outside the norm. DT technology opens up the possibility of obtaining real-time communication with sensor data to monitor food quality and marketability [7].

C. Shrivastava writes that DT technology utilizes real-time sensor data to predict each refrigerated batch's food quality and marketability indicators. Using this approach, the optimal temperature window for shipment can be determined to preserve citrus quality, kill fruit fly larvae, and avoid overcooling of produce [8].

K. J. Dy et al. address DT implementation in the context of supply chains (SC) and failure risks. The authors analyze the literature using implementations in different industry sectors: food, aerospace, automotive, construction, pharmaceutical, and manufacturing [9].

K. S. Hald & P. Coslugeanu investigate the relationship between the COVID-19 pandemic and its implications for global supply chains and their management. The authors identify six supply chain vulnerabilities, six resilience solutions or capabilities, and seven technology clusters considered particularly useful for mitigating future disruptions in a pandemic [10].

L. Xia et al. write that researching the design and application of a smart factory with cross-domain, multiple models has essential implications for smart manufacturing. The authors propose to apply the digital twin system (DTS) architecture to the digital and intelligent modernization of a hydraulic cylinder factory. Experimental results demonstrate the improvement of hydraulic plant, reduction of work-in-progress inventory and faster delivery time [11].

M. Xiong and H. Wang point out that the aviation industry faces challenges including digital transformation, high manufacturing operating costs, and low maintenance efficiency.

The authors conclude that DT are the most widely used in manufacturing and maintenance. High-precision modeling, integration with new IT and human-machine interaction are key technologies in aviation [12].

A. Holzwarth et al. focus on the current challenges of digital supply chains in the manufacturing industry and how to address them. The authors discuss a case study using the SupplyOn supplier collaboration system in a Chinese premium car factory, Seres [13].

Thus, investigating the impact of DT on supply chain resilience in crisis or pandemic environments is a relevant research challenge.

This article aims to analyze the potential applications of DT in supply chain shaping.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials of the study were research articles from their peer-reviewed journals (Asia Europe Journal, Frontiers of Engineering Management, Mobile Networks and Applications, Energy Informatics, Nature Food, Operations Management Research, The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, etc.) that cover the latest advances in the field of DT.

The article uses a case study method: the case study of Siemens, a company already applying DT to optimize its supply chains.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

DT technologies are widely adopted in areas such as online monitoring, online optimization using digital flows, and enterprise-wide cost control [14]. They enable predictive cost estimation that can be realized for each component and subsystem. As a result, enterprise-level cost management becomes more efficient.

Among the key technologies that help accelerate realization of DT-based systems are:

- 1) data-driven modeling;
- 2) intelligent sensors;
- 3) machine vision;
- 4) augmented reality (augmented, virtual, mixed);
- 5) methods of working with databases;
- 6) methods of intellectual data analysis;
- 7) cloud computing;
- 8) peripheral computing [15].

From the perspective of this study, applying DT to form logistics chains seems interesting.

Using twins for the transportation and logistics industry is compelling. For instance, implementing digital inventory in logistics and warehousing complexes leads to a 10% reduction in capital costs and a 30% reduction in operating costs [16].

As companies optimize a wide range of supply chain functions using DT, the technology is gaining acceptance in this area. However, to date, this is an area where DT are underutilized, partly due to a misunderstanding of the technology's applications, capabilities and potential.

However, when implemented correctly and intelligently, DT can provide considerable benefits in shaping and extending supply chains.

The most common applications of digital twin technology in supply chain formation are in core functional areas, such as supply chain planning (DT are embedded in an integrated business planning platform, helping improve supply chain planning, from operational and tactical planning to strategic decision making). DT utilize multiple data sources to enhance transparency and communication between trading partners, and complement statistical data stored in the enterprise resource of the planning platform [17]. In this way, a real-time flow of data, including financial and commercial data, is transferred. As a result, the company can dynamically track inventory changes in warehouses, manage the location of goods in real time, and predict and more accurately direct demand to improve stakeholder engagement [Ibid].

However, the principal value of DT in the supply chain lies in the ability to plan for the long term and make strategic decisions. With this capability, a company can analyze different scenarios to assess risks better and prepare plans to address potential disruptions, settle supply and demand, optimize the balance between sustainability and efficiency, and explore the return on costly investments over multiple time horizons [18].

Companies use DT in supply chain formation to optimize their transportation fleet, asset utilization, and resource allocation. They also strengthen their ability to predict better, detect, and minimize disruptions and failures, such as in warehouse management. Integrated into a warehouse automation system, DT can be deployed in several applications, from inventory management to facilities engineering. Companies are now looking to use DT to simulate their warehouses and help virtually test various floor modeling plans to achieve optimal final facility design before investing heavily in construction [19].

By simulating numerous what-if scenarios, DT can consider factors such as facility location, customer profile, and demand characteristics to help a company determine a uniquely appropriate design for each warehouse. Online retailers can use DT to simulate an existing product delivery system in real time by modeling the results of a potential layout and modifying them through virtual replicas [20]. This can help make accurate and cost-effective decisions without disrupting the real-world facility.

While DT can bring significant business value to warehouse and distribution center design, the impact of the technology becomes more critical in the long term, in conjunction with inventory operations. In warehouse management technology, a digital version of a warehouse receives operational data from a physical facility that is sensitive to the Internet of Things infrastructure. The DT supports warehouse management, inventory, and workflow management, as well as warehouse equipment allocation [21]. The result is improved storage space utilization, increased operational efficiency, and enhanced safety standards in the workplace.

With the help of DT technology, the company tracks the movement of materials and pallet movements during loading, optimizes the design and resource allocation, and offers operational and strategic information for real-time decision making [22]. All of the above increases efficiency and flexibility in shaping the supply chain.

DT can also study the interests of individual customers and changes in consumer behavior, such as delivery and packaging preferences, the number of orders shipped and received, and delivery driver interactions, and analyze driver behavior and safety on the road. In addition, DT enable dynamic optimization of route and navigation tasks and manage dynamic capacity allocation.

DT have a wide range of applications in supply chain optimization, and Siemens is one prominent example.

Siemens uses DT to model and optimize manufacturing processes and supply chains. With DT, they can create a virtual model of their plants and production lines, allowing them to analyze and predict system behavior in real time.

For example, when launching a new product, Siemens can use a DT to simulate various production scenarios, including changes in demand, supply delays and other factors. This allows the company to identify bottlenecks and optimize processes, ultimately reducing costs and increasing efficiency.

In addition, DT help Siemens with inventory management, allowing it to forecast requirements and minimize surpluses more accurately. This leads to a more flexible and resilient supply chain that can quickly adapt to changes in the market.

By applying DT to supply chains, companies can improve operational performance and enhance customer service.

Thus, with the help of DT technologies, modern industry is empowered to solve a wide range of online problems covering all interrelated aspects of an enterprise: research and development, manufacturing and assembly, marketing and sales. In the coming years, as awareness of the economic benefits of DT technology grows, it will be increasingly applied in various fields to stimulate industrial restructuring and modernization.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The use of DT in supply chain optimization has several advantages. In particular, manufacturing companies can use DT to optimize processes, reduce costs, and improve efficiency. Real-time route optimization and inventory management can minimize delays and congestion. With growing interest in sustainability and environmental aspects of business, DT can help companies reduce their carbon footprint and improve supply chain resilience by holistically managing resources and environmental impact.

The role of DT in supply chain optimization is becoming increasingly important. They can significantly reduce risk, improve efficiency and promote agility. Implementing such technologies will undoubtedly be a hot topic for research and practice initiatives in the coming years.

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